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Addendum to: Determination of a new spring-flying species of the *Pterourus glaucus* complex (Papilionidae) in southern New England

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After description of *Pterourus bjorkae* (Pavulaan, 2024) it was subsequently decided to deposit the holotype (female) and allotype (male) in the McGuire Center for Lepidoptera and Biodiversity, Gainesville, Florida. 19 paratypes remain in the collection of the present author. Paratypes in the collection of Alex Grkovich have been transferred to the collection of C. Howard Grisham, Huntsville, Alabama. The holotype (female) bears a red label and the allotype (male) bears a blue label as shown below:

<p><i>Pterourus bjorkae</i> ♀ HOLOTYPE May 15, 1990 Great Swamp Management Area West Kingston, Rhode Island Washington Co. coll./det: H. Pavulaan</p>	<p><i>Pterourus bjorkae</i> ♂ ALLOTYPE June 3, 1984 Great Swamp Management Area West Kingston, Rhode Island Washington Co. coll./det: H. Pavulaan</p>
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LITERATURE CITED

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